

Peers and Familiar Predictors of Inappropriate Dressing among Undergraduate Students

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship among peer pressure, family background, and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students of Delta State University, Abraka Campus. To guide the study, four research questions were raised and three hypotheses formulated. The study adopted a correlational research design and employed a multi-stage sampling method to select 370 respondents from a population of 34,338 students across 12 faculties. Data were collected using a validated and reliable questionnaire and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), and regression statistics. Findings revealed that the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students is high. The study found a significant relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing. Family background was also significantly related to inappropriate dressing. Finally, the analysis established that peer pressure and family background jointly significantly predict inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students. The study recommended amongst others, that Guidance counsellors should design regular sensitization programs, including seminars and workshops, to educate students on the importance of modest dressing and its impact on personal image, employability, and academic environment.

Keywords: Peers; Family Background; Inappropriate Dressing; Undergraduate Students.

Introduction

Inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students has become a pressing concern in many higher institutions, particularly in Nigeria. This phenomenon refers to the adoption of clothing styles that expose sensitive body parts or deviate from socially and culturally acceptable norms. It is increasingly prevalent among young people, especially undergraduates, who are often in a phase of exploration, identity formation, and self-expression. The problem has attracted widespread attention because it not only raises moral questions but also has implications for students' academic performance, social interactions, and institutional image (Foyoh & Martha, 2020).

The need to study inappropriate dressing is justified by its multidimensional effects. Research suggests that dressing styles influence how students are perceived and treated within academic and social settings. For instance, Fileborn (2017) reported that women who

dressed in revealing clothing were more prone to harassment and assault, with many cases accompanied by victim-blaming attitudes (Abbey-Lambertz, 2014). Similarly, King (2015) observed that inappropriate dressing could serve as a distraction that undermines students' focus and overall academic performance. In addition, dressing patterns contribute to the erosion of cultural values. Traditional African dress emphasizes modesty and cultural identity, yet many students have abandoned these values for Western styles that prioritize fashion and exposure over decency (Jacob, 2020). This tension between traditional values and modern fashion trends underscores the urgency of scholarly inquiry.

Empirical studies have examined various predictors of dressing patterns among young people. Newman (2001) and Brown (2004) showed that peer norms exert a strong influence on adolescents and undergraduates, with students often adopting styles to gain acceptance or avoid rejection. Laursen (2018) and Laursen and Veenstra (2021) further emphasized that peer influence is a neutral process, capable of shaping both adaptive and maladaptive behaviors. Family background has also been identified as a significant determinant. Musyoka (2017) found that students from conservative families were less likely to adopt revealing dress styles, while those from liberal backgrounds prioritized self-expression in clothing choices. Other studies highlight the role of media, religion, and cultural orientation in promoting fashion trends that may conflict with indigenous values (Anierobi, Chukwuemeka, Eluemuno, & Nwikpo, 2021; Oli, 2017; Olorunda, 2022).

Despite these insights, important gaps remain. First, much of the existing research has focused on the role of media and Western influence, with fewer studies investigating how peer influence and family background interact to shape inappropriate dressing among Nigerian undergraduates. Second, while studies acknowledge the negative outcomes of inappropriate dressing, little is known about how these predictors jointly impact students' behavior within institutional contexts. This gap necessitates a study that systematically examines the combined influence of peers and family on students' dressing patterns, particularly in a cultural setting where traditional values are under threat from modernization and globalization.

This study is underpinned by Social Learning Theory (SLT), proposed by Albert Bandura (1977, 1986), which posits that individuals acquire behaviors, values, and attitudes through observation, imitation, and modeling within social contexts. The theory assumes that learning can occur vicariously by watching others, that cognitive processes mediate the adoption of new behaviors, and that reinforcement or punishment shapes whether observed behaviors are repeated. It also emphasizes reciprocal determinism, whereby individuals both influence and are influenced by their environment. Within the context of this study, Social Learning Theory explains how undergraduate students' dressing patterns are shaped by their social environment, particularly their peers and families. Students often observe the fashion choices of friends, colleagues, or influential figures and may adopt similar styles to gain approval or avoid rejection. At the same time, family values and parental guidance provide an initial framework that either encourages modesty or permits liberal self-expression in dressing. Thus, inappropriate dressing among undergraduates can be seen as a learned behavior, reinforced within peer networks and family contexts, and sustained by the broader campus culture. This theoretical lens is therefore well suited to understanding how peer

influence and family background predict inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students.

In view of the above, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between peer influence, family background, and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students. By doing so, it intends to provide empirical evidence that will guide educational institutions in developing policies and sensitization programs aimed at promoting culturally acceptable and academically conducive dress standards.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?
2. What is the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?
3. What's the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?
4. What is the relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study;

1. There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus
2. There is no significant relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus
3. There is no significant relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus

Methods

This study adopted the correlational research design. The population for the study comprises 34,338 undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. Given the nature and size of the population of this study, a total of 370 undergraduate students was selected as the sample. The multistage sampling procedure was adopted to ensure that the sample was representative of the diverse academic disciplines within Delta State University, Abraka Campus. The entire population of undergraduate students was first grouped according to faculties. Out of the numerous faculties in DELSU, Abraka Campus, twelve (12) faculties were purposively selected to reflect a broad cross-section of academic disciplines. Within

each of the selected faculties, two departments were chosen using the simple random sampling technique (balloting method with replacement). This gave a total of twenty-four (24) departments, ensuring that each department had an equal chance of being included in the study. From each of the twenty-four (24) selected departments, a proportionate number of students was drawn using convenience sampling based on availability and willingness to participate. This method yielded approximately fifteen to sixteen (15–16) students per department, resulting in the overall sample size of 370 undergraduate students.

Questionnaire was designed as the instrument for collecting data. The questionnaire was divided into two sections; A and B. Section A consists of students' demographic data such as; gender, faculty and department. Section B consists of 41 items derived which measure the variables of the study. The items were further reduced to 31 after validity and reliability. The questionnaire employed a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The type of validity used for the instrument is the face and content validity. The questionnaire designed by the researchers was submitted to experts in Guidance and Counselling for necessary corrections and verifications. The corrections were made by the experts which was taken into cognizance in drafting the final copy of the questionnaire. In order to estimate the reliability of the instrument, 30 copies of the questionnaire were pilot tested on students from Oleh Campus in Delta State University. The data obtained from the pilot study were subjected to a reliability test using the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient. A coefficient of 0.76, 0.63 and 0.49 for peer pressure rating scale, family background rating scale and indecent dressing rating scale respectively.

The researchers administered the questionnaires to the respondents at their respective hostels. The questionnaire was collected on the spot after it has been duly filled. The informed consent of the respondents was obtained; they were assured of the confidentiality of the information they provide. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question 1, Pearson's coefficient of determination was used to answer research questions 2 and 3, while multiple regression was used to answer research question 4. Linear regression statistics was used to test hypotheses 1 and 2 while multiple regression was used to test hypothesis 3. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Clothes that show too much skin are not suitable for an academic environment	3.22	0.82	High
2	Fashion today pays more attention to trends than to cultural or moral values	3.16	0.65	High
3	The way a person dresses affects how others respond to respect them	3.14	0.77	High
4	School should create more awareness about responsible dressing	3.10	0.89	High
5	They should be rules in schools to control what students wear	2.99	0.89	High
6	Wearing revealing clothes is now a normal trend among many young	2.98	0.67	High

7	people Schools should be firm about enforcing codes among students	2.92	0.83	High
Average Mean		3.07	0.79	High
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 1 presents a mean analysis of the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. The findings indicate that the mean scores range from 2.92 to 3.22, with an overall average mean of 3.07. Given that the criterion mean is set at 2.50, these results suggest that the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus is high.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?

Table 2: Correlation and coefficient of determination of the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus

Variable	n	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Peer Pressure					
Inappropriate dressing	120	0.42	0.18	1.8	Positive Relationship

Table 2 shows a Pearson’s coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. The result shows an r-value of 0.42 and r²-value of 0.18. The result revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. Peer pressure contributed 1.8% to the variability in inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. This implies that there is relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus.

Research Question 3: What’s the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?

Table 3: Correlation and coefficient of determination of the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus

Variable	n	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Family Background					
Inappropriate dressing	120	0.39	0.15	1.5	Positive Relationship

Table 3 shows a Pearson’s coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. The result shows an r-value of 0.39 and r²-value of 0.15. The result revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. Family

background contributed 1.5% to the variability in inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. This implies that there is relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus.

Research Question 4: What’s the relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus?

Table 4: Correlation and coefficient of determination of the relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus

Variable	N	R	R ²	R ² %	Decision
Peer Pressure					
Family Background	120	0.50	0.25	2.5	Positive Relationship
Inappropriate dressing					

Table 4 shows a Pearson’s coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. The result shows an r-value of 0.50 and r²-value of 0.25. The result revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. Peer pressure and family background contributed 2.5% to the variability in inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. This implies that there is relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus

Table 5: Regression analysis of the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	161.408	1	161.408	25.443	.000 ^b
Residual	748.584	118	6.344		
Total	909.992	119			

Variables in Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig	
	B	Beta			
Constant	6.292		1.446	4.352	.000
Peer Pressure	.186	.421	.037	5.004	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = 0.42$, $R\text{-Square} = 0.18$

a. Dependent Variable: Inappropriate dressing

b. Predictors (Constant): Peer Pressure

Table 5 shows a regression analysis of the relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The result shows that $F(1, 119) = 25.443$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between peer pressure and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The R^2 value of 0.42 showed that 18% of the variance in inappropriate dressing was accounted for by peer pressure. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for predicting inappropriate dressing from peer pressure is 0.186; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.421, $t = 5.044$. Peer pressure is significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between Family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus.

Table 6: Regression analysis of the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	136.564	1	136.564	20.835	.000 ^b
Residual	773.428	118	6.554		
Total	909.992	119			

Variables in Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig	
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	21.722	1.818		11.947	.000
Family Background	-.336	.074	-.387	-4.565	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = 0.39$, $R\text{-Square} = 0.15$

a. Dependent Variable: Inappropriate dressing

b. Predictors (Constant): Family Background

Table 6 shows a regression analysis of the relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The result shows that $F(1, 119) = 20.835$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The R^2 value of 0.39 showed that 15% of the variance in inappropriate dressing was accounted for by family background. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for predicting inappropriate dressing from peer pressure is -0.336; the standardized coefficient (β) is -0.387, $t = -4.565$. Peer pressure is significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus

Table 7: Regression analysis of the relationship among peer pressure and Family background indecent among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	230.100	2	115.050	19.798	.000 ^b
Residual	679.892	117	5.811		
Total	909.992	118			

Variables in Equation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
	B	Beta		
Constant	13.665		5.330	.000
Peer Pressure	.148	.336	4.012	.000
Family Background	-.250	-.288	-3.438	.001

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = 0.50$, $R\text{-Square} = 0.25$

a. Dependent Variable: Inappropriate dressing

b. Predictors (Constant): Peer Pressure; Family Background

Table 7 shows a regression analysis of the relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The result shows that $F(2, 118) = 19.798$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship among peer pressure, family background and inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University Abraka Campus. The R^2 value of 0.50 showed that 25% of the variance in inappropriate dressing was accounted for by peer pressure and family background. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for predicting inappropriate dressing from peer pressure and family background is 0.148 and -.250 respectively; the standardized coefficient (β) for peer pressure is 0.336 and -.288 for family background, $t = 4.012$ for peer pressure and $t = -3.438$. Peer pressure and family background is significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Discussions

The first finding revealed that the prevalence of inappropriate dressing among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus is high. This indicates that inappropriate dressing has become a widespread practice on campus, reflecting shifts in values, fashion trends, and social norms that conflict with cultural, moral, and institutional expectations. This aligns with Omede (2021), who noted that inappropriate dressing is increasingly common in universities, where students perceive campus life as a platform for self-expression. The influence of globalization, western media, and liberal youth culture has popularized provocative styles—such as micro-mini skirts, sagging trousers, and tight-fitting clothing—that clash with traditional values of modesty.

The second finding revealed a significant relationship between peer influence and inappropriate dressing among undergraduates. This shows that students’ dressing patterns are strongly shaped by the desire to conform to peer group standards. The finding supports Santor et al. (2020), who observed that young people are more likely to adopt peer-approved

behaviors even when they conflict with parental or cultural expectations. In many Nigerian universities, peer groups valorize revealing fashion trends, leading students to adopt inappropriate dressing as a means of gaining acceptance, signaling group identity, or elevating social status. This also echoes Omede (2021) and Nwogwugwu and Eze (2020), who found that peer norms often override parental guidance.

The third finding revealed a significant relationship between family background and inappropriate dressing. This indicates that parental guidance, socio-economic status, family structure, and moral upbringing play key roles in shaping students' appearance. This agrees with Adewale and Ogunleye (2019), who emphasized that family background is a major determinant of students' values and behaviors, including dressing styles. Similarly, Adebayo (2020) and Ekwulugo and Chukwu (2020) found that strong religious and cultural foundations promote modest dressing, while weak family supervision and liberal orientations increase the likelihood of inappropriate dressing.

The fourth finding revealed that there is a combined effect of peer influence and family background on inappropriate dressing among undergraduates. This suggests that inappropriate dressing is not shaped by a single factor, but by the interaction of social and familial contexts. The finding corroborates Olowu (2021), who highlighted the interplay between peer dynamics and family upbringing in shaping students' dressing choices. It also resonates with Uche and Nwafor (2022), who reported that weak family communication and supervision predispose students to succumb to peer pressure, as well as with Ibrahim and Yusuf (2020), who found that poor family support and low self-esteem increase susceptibility to inappropriate dressing.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that inappropriate dressing is highly prevalent among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka Campus. It also concludes that both peer influence and family background are significant predictors of inappropriate dressing. While peer influence often drives conformity to provocative fashion trends on campus, family background provides the initial values and frameworks that can either deter or encourage such dressing patterns. Importantly, the combined effect of peer and family contexts demonstrates that inappropriate dressing results from the interaction of both social and familial influences:

1. Guidance and Counseling units should organize regular workshops and seminars to educate students on the benefits of modest dressing and its implications for personal image, employability, and the academic environment.
2. Peer mentoring initiatives should be established, where trained student leaders serve as role models to promote positive dressing habits and reduce the negative effects of peer influence.

3. Parents and guardians should be sensitized through family engagement programs about their roles in shaping students' values, moral discipline, and clothing choices.
4. Guidance and Counseling services should adopt a holistic approach that integrates family values, peer group dynamics, and personal development strategies in addressing inappropriate dressing among undergraduates.

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